

GL MICAVE

D7.1 GLOMICAVE Website

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1.0	20/12/2020	EUT	Final report

Executive summary

This deliverable explains how Eurecat, responsible of the Task 7.2 Communication activities, has developed GLOMICAVE project webpage. The document summarises the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project. Also, the data protection measures adopted within the site.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>BDA</i>	<i>Big Data Analytics</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

INTRODUCTION

GLOMICAVE is a 3-year and a half project aiming at **addressing the need to build systems to allow the use of primary data analytical processes and support large-scale omic experiments**, maximising the utility of omic data at a massive level and increasing the understanding of biological systems as a whole.

The project will develop an **innovative digital cloud-based genotype to phenotype platform** relying on Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omics datasets. This platform has the objective to assist experts and non-experts in identifying and understanding new links between genotype and phenotype.

Eurecat is the partner leader of the **Task 7.2 Communication Activities (M01-M42)** and is responsible to **design and develop the GLOMICAVE's website** which will contain general information on the project, the main outputs, public reports and scientific publications, news, events attended by the partners and dissemination materials.

This document presents and explains how the project's webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. The deliverable summarises the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

PROJECT WEBSITE

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing the official GLOMICAVE project website. The registered URL is www.glomicave.eu.

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. The website will be the anchor for all communication activities related to the project and will serve as a central point of entry for all public material, including the project's basic information, expected impacts and objectives. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active during three years after its end to support the exploitation of the project.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project and it gives access to GLOMICAVE social media channels (Twitter so far).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use Wordpress, as the Eurecat's Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website languages, the basis is English but if a need to translate some parts of the website arise, a multilingual plugin will be installed for this purpose.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

1. Website structure

The following information architecture for GLOMICAVE website is proposed in the figure below. In green, you can see the pages/structure that have been created for the website launch, while, in blue, the pages that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Further changes to the website structure may be made in the future to allocate documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

Figure 1: GLOMICAVE website structure

2. Website content

The texts hereinafter describe the contents published on the first version of the website.

2.1 Homepage

It includes two sliders: “*Global omic data integration on animal, vegetal and environment sectors*” and “*Developing a cloud-based genotype to phenotype platform based on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence*”

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, its main objectives and key outputs, as well as a section on the context.

In addition, a section mentioning the consortium linking to the partners page has been designed and included in the homepage.

As soon as the “News & Events” section have some new articles and contents, a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s twitter feed will be created. Specific sections will be created to promote and divulge the platform and services created during the project.

GLOMICAVE in a nutshell

Developing an innovative multi-omics data analysis open digital platform

GLOMICAVE project develops a new **digital genotype to phenotype platform, relying on Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence** and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omic datasets.

The project addresses the need to build systems that allow the **use of primary data analytical processes and support large-scale omic experiments**, thus **maximising the utility of omic data at a massive level and understanding of biological systems** as a whole.

BUTTON – FIND OUT MORE – link to “About GLOMICAVE” page

GLOMICAVE ambition

Our goal is to provide a technology platform to support data integration for identifying and associating new links between animal and vegetable genotype and phenotype.

Business cases

GLOMICAVE integrative approach will be validated in **three different industrial sectors – livestock, agro-biotechnology and environment** - addressing specific challenges in **6 business cases**:

- Animal reproductive technology
- Meat quality
- Fruit growth and quality
- Plant growth
- Phosphorus removal and recovery
- Bioenergy production in the urban water cycle

BUTTON – LEARN MORE – link to “Business cases” page

News & Events

This section will include a Twitter widget and will show the latest news and events published on the project's website.

Partners

GLOMICAVE multidisciplinary consortium is made up of **15 partners from 6 European countries**. **5** research institutions, **5** SMEs, **3** universities, **1** animal cluster and **1** standardisation body.

LOGOS PARTNERS

BUTTON – KNOW THE WHOLE CONSORTIUM – link to “Partners” page

MULTI-OMICS DATA ANALYSIS

Global omic data integration on animal, vegetal and environment sectors

[More information](#)

ABOUT THE PROJECT
GLOMICAVE PLATFORM

GLOMICAVE IN A NUTSHELL

Developing an innovative multi-omics data analysis open digital platform

GLOMICAVE project develops a new digital genotype to phenotype platform, relying on Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omic datasets.

The project addresses the need to build systems that allow the use of primary data analytical processes and support large-scale omic experiments, thus maximising the utility of omic data at a massive level and understanding of biological systems as a whole.

<p>+</p> <p>About the project</p> <p>Increasing the understanding of biological systems</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>🖥️</p> <p>Our platform</p> <p>An innovative multi-omics data analysis open platform</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>🧪</p> <p>Omic sciences</p> <p>Scientific discipline studying biochemistry and molecular biology</p> <p>Read more</p>
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GLOMICAVE ambition

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GLOMICAVE business cases

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- Animal reproductive technology
- Meat quality
- Fruit growth and quality
- Plant growth
- Phosphorus removal and recovery
- Bioenergy production in the urban water cycle

[Find out more >](#)

Contact us!

Contact us to receive more information about the latest news and developments of GLOMICAVE project

[Get in touch >](#)

News & Events

GLOMICAVE project Kicks off!

Meeting - December 2, 2019

Nulla a velit quis ex omare rhoncus. Donec imperdiet risus justo, vel malesuada erat fermentum at. Morbi at laoreet mauris. Mauris lorem felis, gravida et vehicula congue, tempus vel justo.

[Read more >](#)

Our team

GLOMICAVE interdisciplinary consortium is made up of 15 partners from 6 European countries: 5 research institutions, 5 industry partners, 3 universities, 1 animal cluster and 1 standardisation body.

Eurecat

Alice

ASINCAR

TREE Technology

AKiNaO

University of Minho

SERIDA

Aalborg University

UNE

INRAE

Figure 2: View of GLOMICAVE homepage <https://glomicave.eu/>

2.2 About GLOMICAVE

This section includes the main information on the project, the main goals and the expected impacts. Additionally, when promotional materials (leaflet, rollup, etc), deliverables and other audiovisual materials are produced, specific sub-pages will be created to allocate them.

The content of the page is divided in the following sub-sections / areas:

2.2.1 GLOMICAVE project

Increasing the understanding of biological systems

The GLOMICAVE project aims to **combine and analyse different types of omic data** (genomics, metabolomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics), to obtain relevant information and **discover new links between animal and vegetable genotype and phenotype**.

To do so, the project will apply **Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence techniques** to develop a **multi-omics data analysis open platform** [[LINK TO PLATFORM PAGE](#)] consisting of multiple tools to maximise the use of omics data at a massive level and to support large-scale omic experiments.

The main innovation behind GLOMICAVE relies on **demonstrating the integration of different omics databases with specific information available in other supports**, to allow a better understanding of the many sources of genotype-phenotype associations and, as a result, a more accurate phenotypic prediction.

Start date: 1 November 2020. End date: 30 April 2024 (42 months).

Funded under: [H2020-EU.2.1.4](#)

Project concept

GLOMICAVE aims to combine scientific knowledge from bibliographic public repositories and biological datasets to feed the data integration platform for experimental multi-omics.

BUTTON – GLOMICAVE PLATFORM – link to “Platform” page

Objectives

- Create a strategy for integrating multi-omics datasets in a harmonised and normalised manner.
- Analyse the existing investigation and literature, by using text mining and Natural Language Processing (NLP), to promote a strategy for extracting knowledge on multi-omics (genotype-phenotype) relations.
- Promote a multi-omics computational integration strategy based on multivariate algorithms.
- Discover and show unknown genotype-phenotype links.
- Develop a holistic and meaningful user-centred cloud-based Big Data platform for multi-omics integration and genotype-phenotype association.

ABOUT GLOMICAVE

THE PROJECT

Increasing the understanding of biological systems

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Funded under
Horizon 2020 Programme - H2020-EU.2.1.4

Project concept

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[The platform >](#)

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- Analyse the existing investigation and literature, by using text mining and Natural Language Processing (NLP), to promote a strategy for extracting knowledge on multi-omics (genotype-phenotype) relations.
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- Develop a multi-omics computational integration strategy based on multivariate algorithms.
- Develop a holistic and meaningful user-centred cloud-based Big Data platform for multi-omics integration and genotype-phenotype association.

Business cases

Three industrial sectors addressing specific challenges in 6 business cases

Animal	Vegetal	Environment
Two business cases focused on livestock, the fertility level of these animals and the beef cattle quality	Two business cases to predict fruit quality and to identify biomarkers in order to improve yield	The water-environment business cases are focused to identify and characterise of microbes and microbial

[Find out more >](#)

Contact us! info@glomicave.eu [Online contact form](#)

Figure 3: View of About GLOMICAVE page <https://glomicave.eu/about-glomicave/>

2.2.2 Omic sciences

This section is devoted to explaining briefly the omic sciences, its importance and the main sectors in which they can be applied.

Omic sciences refer to a scientific discipline which **studies biochemistry and molecular biology, including existing technologies and some more recent ones such as epigenetics and metagenomics for studying microbiota**, with advances in computational solutions applied to bioinformatics.

The omic disciplines **provide important breakthroughs in the knowledge and understanding of biological aspects and issues**, representing a huge development in the area of the analysis of cell functionality and biotechnological applications.

In recent years, omic sciences have become an essential tool to **promote the innovation of different sectors, such as the food industry, environment, or health and biotechnology**, in which products or substances of biological origin play an important role.

- Metabolomics: studying metabolites and metabolic products
- Genomics: studying the genome and the function of genes
- Proteomics: studying the structure, function location and interaction of proteins
- Lipidomics: studying the lipid species located in a cell or biological system
- Transcriptomics: studying mRNA and gene expressions

Benefits of the omic sciences

- **Technological improvement and innovation:** new opportunities of innovation for companies and entities in different fields.
- **Personalisation:** allowing to obtain more individualised treatments, especially in the field of personalised nutrition.
- **Product development:** creating new products with more health impacts that satisfy social trends and consumer needs.
- **Expanded knowledge:** providing a deep knowledge and understanding of the system biology and the mechanism of action.
- **Transversality:** omic technologies could be applied in a huge variety of sectors and applications.

Sectors and applications

1. **Health and Nutrition**
2. **Food**
3. **Agriculture**
4. **Environment**
5. **Sports and wellbeing**

BUTTON – GLOMICAVE BUSINESS CASES – link to “Business cases” page

OMIC SCIENCES

What are omic sciences?

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- 2 **Genomics:** studying the genome and the function of genes
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Sectors and applications

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[GLOMICAVE business cases](#) >

-
Health & Nutrition
-
Food
-
Environment
-
Agriculture
-
Sport
-
Wellbeing

Figure 4: View of Omic Sciences page <https://glomicave.eu/omic-sciences/>

Partners

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. This page includes a first section with a brief description of the consortium, followed by a portfolio with the logos of the different partners, leading to a specific page per partners with their contact details.

GLOMICAVE project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising of **15 partners from 6 different** European countries providing the necessary range of expertise, competence and operational capacity to achieve the innovative project objectives.

5 research institutions, **5** industry partners, **3** universities, **1** animal cluster and **1** standardisation body.

Eurecat

 Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The center offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

With a vast experience in developing innovative solutions based on omics sciences and Big Data analytics, Eurecat is the project coordinator and leads the development of multivariate methods for multi-omics data analysis and the platform monitoring, security and governance. We are also responsible for the user interface design and frontend implementations, managing IPR and exploitation activities and the project's communication tasks.

www.eurecat.org

Twitter: [@Eurecat_News](https://twitter.com/Eurecat_News)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ_t_6ozc7bDaKZw

Alice

Alice is a union of cooperatives which unites all the French animal selection and reproduction companies and also a Belgian selection company. Some of these companies are world leaders in the sector.

Alice represents and defends all the cattle, sheep and goat insemination sectors nationally, in Europe and internationally. It also conducts research programmes in partnership with INRA or private research companies to progress knowledge and techniques in the fields of reproduction physiology and animal genetic selection. Finally, it carries out the tasks of advice, technical support and training for all its members.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

For 20 years, Alice has acquired expertise in reproductive physiology, embryos biotechnologies and different “-omics” technologies. Thus, as SME involved in animal reproduction and genetic sector, Alice is leading the work-package dedicated to the business applications and particularly involved in animal reproduction case in collaboration with Serida and Eurecat. Moreover, Alice is also involved in the development of the GLOMICAVE platform and other cross-cutting work-packages.

www.alice.fr

Twitter: [@Alice_Elevage](https://twitter.com/Alice_Elevage)

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/alice/>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/alice_elevage/

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGsQrwDwnsl-LUCp3ddtYBA>

TREE

Tree Technology (TREE) is an R&D-performing SME providing information and communication technology solutions based on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (e.g., machine learning and analytics, computer vision, NLP, visual analytics, data management).

TREE provides ICT-based solutions for different sectors and markets such as healthcare, banking, and insurance. TREE commercializes tailor-made solutions/services exploited under the brand 'Treelogic'. TREE works within an open innovation model where cooperative R&D activities are key to assess the maturity of emerging technologies, gathering new and differential knowledge. The company has participated in more than 20 European R&D projects.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

With large expertise in Big Data solutions, TREE will be the integrator of the cloud-based Big Data platform for the collection, storage, processing and exploitation of data from the different -omic sources, coming from both end users and public repositories. This will facilitate the data ingestion, preparation and analysis. TREE will act as the technical manager of the project.

www.treetk.com/en/

www.treelogic.com/en/

Twitter: [@tree_RD](https://twitter.com/tree_RD)

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/treelogic/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/user/TreelogicTIC>

UNE

The Spanish Association for Standardization, UNE, is legally designated as the National Standardization Body of Spain. It is the national representative and member of the European (CEN and CENELEC), International (ISO and IEC) and Pan-American (COPANT) Standards Organizations, and member of the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

Through the development of technical standards helps improving the quality, competitiveness and innovation of companies, products and services.

UNE has a large experience in supporting research and innovation communities when taking advantage of standards and standardization to increase the impact of their activities, approaching their results to the industry, society and market environments.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

UNE will advise, manage and develop all the activities related with standardization as a tool for knowledge transfer.

www.une.org

Twitter: [@NormasUNE](https://twitter.com/NormasUNE)

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/une-asociaci%C3%B3n-espa%C3%B1ola-de-normalizaci%C3%B3n/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCI1cbwOPrFUxcq4yf61jIzw>

INRAE

The French National Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) ranked as No. 1 globally, and its third party [University of Bordeaux](https://www.univ-bordeaux.fr/) participate through UMR1332 Fruit Biology and Pathology (BFP) with topics ranging from understanding mechanisms underlying the development of plants or their interaction with pathogens or the environment to the application of this knowledge into translational research.

The BFP-Metabolism team conducts internationally recognised research centred on metabolism and plant performance that combines modelling and experimentation.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

BFP-Metabolism team will provide and complete a unique dataset comprising multilevel analyses for 10 fruit species during growth and ripening. It has strong leadership in plant systems biology, more specifically metabolomics, and develops models that predict plant performance under optimal and stress conditions in order to dissect the underlying metabolic mechanisms. As such, BFP will lead WP4, in which analysis, mining and modelling of multi-omics data are key, in order to unravel unprecedented relationships between genotypes and phenotypes.

<https://www.inrae.fr/en>

Twitter: [@INRAE_France](https://twitter.com/INRAE_France) [@bdxPlantMetabo](https://twitter.com/bdxPlantMetabo)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Inrae.France/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/test-science/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCQxx5pTHLCoxjrr6VhLznRw>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/INRAE/>

SERIDA

SERIDA is a public institute of the Principality of Asturias (Spain) which aims to contribute to the modernization and improvement of the capacities of the regional agri-food sector by promoting and carrying out agri-food technological research and demonstrative activities, in order to transfer innovations to the main stakeholders, facilitating improvements in productivity, promoting a diversification of the sector and increasing economic benefits through the value chain.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

SERIDA is responsible of the identification of biomarkers predictive of pregnancy and calving outcomes in cattle including deciphering the complex embryo-recipient interactions.

SERIDA will develop applications for livestock focused on efficient use of ET in cattle embryo transfer. SERIDA will provide unique expertise in Metabolomics solutions and Physiology to counteract cattle infertility and improve the efficiency of genomics selection programs.

SERIDA will also participate in the identification of relevant databases, and extraction of meaningful information applicable to animal reproductive technology, leading to identification of relevant metabolites and definition of relevant genotypes and phenotypes and pathways. SERIDA will in turn contribute to develop “in silico” predictive models for animal reproduction.

www.serida.org/

Twitter: [@SeridaAst](https://twitter.com/SeridaAst)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/SeridaAst/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGkoP7HF3_nluaDCEeGrd7g/featured

ASINCAR

ASINCAR is the Agrifood Technology Centre and Business Cluster of Asturias, providing knowledge and technology transfer to the Agrifood sector

ASINCAR offers solutions to the Agrifood companies contributing to their competitiveness, sustainability and their adaptation to future market scenarios through innovation and cooperation. It brings together the expertise of 28 qualified multidisciplinary professionals who generate a volume of income of 2M€ per year. Serving more than 350 companies in the Agrifood sector, ASINCAR is involved in 50 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

Within the project, ASINCAR will collaborate in the integration and processing of information from both Data bases (public) and private datasets, as well as extracting information from scientific papers.

ASINCAR will also participate in the Genotype - Phenotype unknown relations discovery related to the meat quality animal case, as well as in the software validation through industrial cases, within the meat quality characterization in the animal business case. Finally, with the role of Dissemination Manager, ASINCAR will collaborate with other partners in the dissemination and communication activities.

<https://www.asincarc.com/>

Twitter: [@asincarc](https://twitter.com/asincarc)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/asincarcCT>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/asincarc/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/user/Asincarc>

Aalborg University (AAU)

AALBORG UNIVERSITET

Aalborg University (AAU) is the second largest engineering university in Denmark and ranked as the top engineering university in Europe and among top 5 in the world. There are around 20,000 students at campuses in Aalborg, Copenhagen and Esbjerg.

Center for Microbial Communities, Department of Chemistry and Bioscience is carrying out world-class research on microbial communities in various natural and engineered ecosystems. Focus areas are microbial ecology and physiology of novel uncultured microbes and microbial communities, novel methods and applied bioinformatics, primarily for human health and recovery of resources and energy. The Center possesses state of the art omics and visualization equipment and expertise.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

The main contribution of Center for Microbial Communities is microbial ecology and physiology of microbes involved in phosphate and nitrogen removal and recovery related to wastewater treatment. The Center maintains the MiDAS database with information about microbes in global water resource recovery facilities.

<https://www.en.aau.dk/>

Twitter: @AAUBrussels

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/AalborgUniversitet/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/school/aalborg-universitet/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/user/aalborguniversitet>

AkiNaO

AKINA O

Your partner in Natural Substances Chemistry. AkiNaO was created in 2010 in France by three specialists in natural substances. Specialised in the field of Agriculture, AkiNaO was accredited as Good Laboratory Practices in 2017. The activities are organized in 3 poles:

- 1 –Service delivery: Development and validation of analytical methods and Biocontrol products assessment.
- 2- R&D: Biocontrol products from natural origin and development of innovative tools for agriculture. As instance, early detection of sharka disease by metabolomic approaches (AntiShark Project).
- 3- Training division: Development of distance learning platform, MyGreenTrainingBox. Digital courses of high scientific and pedagogical quality.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

AkiNaO has extensive experience and field of application of metabolomic approaches in the field of agriculture. According to these skills, AkiNaO must provide generated data concerning the sharka disease (AntiShark Project) and contribute on genotype-phenotype relationships from multi-omics data. Furthermore, AkiNaO participate as end-user and validator on the results obtained for identification of specific biomarkers of sharka disease using multi-omics data.

<http://www.akinao-lab.com/>

Twitter: [@AkiNaOLab66](https://twitter.com/AkiNaOLab66)

Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/AkiNaOLab/?hc_location=ufi

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/akinao-lab/>

NEC Laboratories

Orchestrating a brighter world

NEC Laboratories Europe (NLE), located in Heidelberg, Germany, pushes the boundaries of technology through original contributions that are published in top scientific conferences and journals in a wide variety of disciplines, including machine learning, data science, security, system platform, IoT, and 5G. Moreover, NLE is passionate about

bringing new ideas to the real world. To this end, NLE collaborates with universities, research institutes, other corporate research centres, and NEC affiliates and business units.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

NLE leverages its expertise in graph AI, open information extraction, and natural language processing to lead efforts to find, obtain, and analyze scientific literature relevant to the project and to extract structured knowledge from unstructured text documents. Furthermore, NLE collaborates with project partners to use multivariate methods for multi-omics data analysis and to discover unknown genotype-phenotype relationships.

<https://neclab.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nec-laboratories-europe-gmbh/>

University of Minho (UMINHO)

University of Minho (UMinho) is a Public Foundation under the legal Regime of Higher Education Institutes. UMinho's mission is to create, spread and put knowledge into application, with free thinking and pluralism as its core values. The fulfillment of the mission is undertaken in an international reference framework, where scientific research plays a leading role in close articulation with teaching.

The **Centre of Biological Engineering (CEB)** is a research centre located at UMinho which combines fundamental science with Engineering Sciences to obtain value-added products or processes in the Food, Chemical, Biotech, and Environmental Industries. CEB is a unit aiming to be a strategic infrastructure for the development of R&D and innovation policies in the areas of Biotechnology and Bioengineering, Biomaterials, Biomedical and Life Sciences, Environmental and Agricultural Sciences. The Bioresources, bioremediation, biorefinery group at CEB (BRIDGE group) is one of the main players of the Portuguese R&D on Environmental Biotechnology with the mission to underpin the transition from a linear to a circular economy by generating, applying and disseminating knowledge and transfer technology in the field of Environmental Biotechnology.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

During last years applied and fundamental research has been performed in CEB-UMinho in the field of environmental biotechnology and anaerobic wastewater treatment, by using a combination of lab-scale/full-scale bioreactors operation, application of microbial culturing and microbial communities profiling techniques, as well as multi-omics approaches to link microbial identity to function in anaerobic microbiomes. CEB-UMinho will participate in the project by linking genotype to phenotype in microbial communities involved in anaerobic digestion.

<https://www.uminho.pt/PT>

Twitter: [@UMinho_Oficial](https://twitter.com/UMinho_Oficial)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/uminhooficial>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidade-do-minho/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAGnIMMRlrpfE-aeZjKJWg>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/universidade_do_minho/

Águas do Norte

Águas do Norte is a large company which manages the multi-municipal system responsible for the collection, treatment and supply of water intended for public consumption and for the collection, treatment and disposal of domestic, urban and industrial effluents.

The exploration and management of these systems includes the design, construction, extension, conservation, repair, renovation, maintenance and improvement of the infrastructures and the acquisition of the equipment and facilities necessary for the development of the activities.

ADN has a coverage area of 66 municipalities in the North of Portugal, serves 3.7 million inhabitants across a territorial region accounting for 22% of Portugal, and integrates the following infrastructures: 29 WTP, 2258 km of water pipelines and 372 water reservoirs, 189 WWTP, 1616 km of sewage drainage systems and 368 sewage pumping stations.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

Águas do Norte will provide samples and operational data from its anaerobic digesters on treatment efficiencies, digestate quality and methane productivity. A sludge digester and a co-digestion digester will be studied by means of metagenomic / metatranscriptomic analyzes, aiming to link the identity and microbial function to the efficiency of bioprocessing.

<http://www.adnorte.pt/>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/aguasdonorte/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/aguasdonorte/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC6uSbxnn_MlfyRiDgpKYsjw

ASEAVA

ASEAVA is a breeder association recognised by the Spanish Agricultural Ministry which main task is the Asturiana de los Valles beef breed Herd book and Breeding program management.

ASEAVA is a non-profit organisation which aims to promote the breed and defend the associated breeder interests through advice, studies, petitions, reports and opinions on the problems inherent to the breeder society competences. The society is organised through 4.207 breeders and 107.818 animals are included in the Herd book. Since 1985, the association is responsible to register phenotypic information on-farm, at the Performance Test Station, and in the Slaughter house and cutting room to be used in the ASEAVA genetic selection program, being one of the pioneer association in Spain for the systematic measuring of phenotypic data in beef cattle. In the present time, ASEAVA has registered phenotypic information of approximately 770.000 individuals. ASEAVA's team includes 22 workers from whom two are veterinarians and 6 are field controllers trained to collect phenotypic data in beef cattle.

Contribution to GLOMICAVE

Within the project, ASEAVA collaborate in the integration and harmonisation of multi-omics data in order to enable access to the data which will be analysed, as well as in the multi-omics data analysis. ASEAVA will also participate in the Genotype - Phenotype unknown relations discovery. ASEAVA will lead the production of meat quality phenotypes as well as omic data and the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication activities.

<https://www.aseava.com/>

Twitter: [@ASEAVAOFICIAL](https://twitter.com/ASEAVAOFICIAL)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/aseava.asturianadelosvalles>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCszwFsDMkYVv593D2gCkd9g>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/aseava01/>

PARTNERS

Meet our team!

GLOMICAVE project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising of 15 partners from 6 different European countries providing the necessary range of expertise, competence and operational capacity to achieve the innovative project objectives.

5	5	3	1	1
Research institutions	Industry partners	Universities	Animal cluster	Standardisation body

Eurecat Read more >	Allice Read more >	TREE Technology Read more >	ASINCAR Read more >
AkiNaO Read more >	Aalborg University Read more >	SERIDA Read more >	University of Minho Read more >

Figure 5: View of part of the partners page <https://glomicave.eu/partners/>

2.2.3 Deliverables & Promotional Materials

This page will include a list of all deliverables to be prepared during the project and will provide access to the executive summary of confidential ones and full access to the public ones. In addition, when the promotional materials will be created this page will also include a section to give access to them.

2.2.4 Audiovisual materials

This page will include the different audiovisual materials that will be prepared during the project and will give access to the YouTube project's channel.

DELIVERABLES

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

WP1 - Integration and harmonisation of multi-omics data

- D1.1 Datasets and repositories benchmarking
- D1.2 GLOMICAVE semantic model
- D1.3 GLOMICAVE Knowledge graph
- D1.4 Data curation mechanisms
- D1.5 GLOMICAVE data lake

WP2 - Text mining and NLP for multi-omics knowledge extraction

- D2.1 Novel training Dataset and labelling functions
- D2.2 Preliminary version of algorithms for extraction and the data pipeline
- D2.3 Final version of algorithms for extraction and the data pipeline

WP3 - Leveraging multivariate methods for multi-omics data analysis

- D3.1 A multi-omics data integration and pathway enrichment module that integrates information from literature and hidden relationships among molecular entities
- D3.2 An advanced metabolite annotation module for untargeted metabolomics data

Figure 6: View of part of deliverables page <https://qlomicave.eu/deliverables/>

2.3 The platform

GLOMICAVE platform

GLOMICAVE applies **Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence technologies** to develop a **holistic cloud-based platform** consisting of three layers: **data integration, data analysis and data exploitation**, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring.

This platform combines scientific knowledge from bibliographic public repositories and biological datasets, in order to feed the data integration platform for experimental multi-omics and become a useful biotechnology tool for genotype-phenotype associations.

- **Data integration:** assessing and processing the datasets resulting from data gathering pipeline, together with the knowledge extracted from scientific repositories.
- **Data analysis:** allowing genotype-phenotype associations analysis and discovery, endowing the platform with capabilities to act as a central knowledge-base of information contained in omics databases and literature.
- **Data exploitation:** new experimental data to be uploaded, integrated with existing knowledge and projected onto biological pathways via an easy-to-use interface and complementary visualisation tools.

Research beyond the state-of-the-art

Massive increases in analytical and reductions in costs have enabled multi-omics analysis and studies to be performed at a scale not previously imagined. However, there are **current limitations and gaps that are preventing a better data integration and genotype-phenotype validation**.

- The lack of integration of the knowledge in scientific literature and databases in an automated way into current genotype-phenotype association solutions.
- The heterogeneity of data generated by the different omics platforms preventing a homogeneous fusion and integration of data.
- The high rate of metabolites that remain unidentified in untargeted metabolomics analysis, preventing a large-scale integration.
- The poor interpretability of the results by different computational genotype-phenotype models.
- Non-biomedical sectors lack of holistic omics science-based integration tools.

GLOMICAVE innovation

GLOMICAVE platform overcomes these problems presenting a **novel and unique integration** of structured data from omics datasets with information without a pre-defined organised model, stored in text documents or similar sources, with a variety of formats.

Platform benefits

- Simple and easy to be used by people with no specific knowledge in data analysis or Artificial Intelligence techniques.
- Modular, flexible and scalable platform, incorporating API services with other existing systems (additional sources, third-party platforms) and providing a common and referent data model to promote data sharing across different tools.
- Adaptable to different business exploitation models, meeting scientific and industry needs and interests.
- It will comply with regulatory and ethical best practices to avoid possible misuses of the GLOMICAVE knowledge.

PLATFORM

GLOMICAVE platform

GLOMICAVE project applies Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence technologies to develop a holistic cloud-based platform consisting of three layers: data integration, data analysis and data exploitation, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring.

This platform combines scientific knowledge from bibliographic public repositories and biological datasets, in order to feed the data integration platform for experimental multi-omics and become a useful biotechnology tool for genotype-phenotype associations.

The benefits

- 1 Simple and easy to be used by people with no specific knowledge in data analysis or Artificial Intelligence techniques.
- 2 Adaptable to different business exploitation models, meeting scientific and industry needs and interests.
- 3 It will comply with regulatory and ethical best practices to avoid possible misuses of the GLOMICAVE knowledge.
- 4 Modular, flexible and scalable platform, incorporating API services with other existing systems (additional sources, third-party platforms) and providing a common and referent data model to promote data sharing across different tools.

1

Data integration

Assessing and processing the datasets resulting from data gathering pipeline, together with the knowledge extracted from scientific repositories.

2

Data analysis

Allowing genotype-phenotype associations analysis, endowing the platform with capabilities to act as a central knowledge-base of information.

3

Data exploitation

New experimental data to be uploaded, integrated with existing knowledge and projected onto biological pathways via an easy-to-use interface.

Research beyond the state-of-the-art

Massive increases in analytical and reductions in costs have enabled multi-omics analysis and studies to be performed at a scale not previously imagined. However, there are **current limitations and gaps that are preventing a better data integration and genotype-phenotype validation.**

- The heterogeneity of data generated by the different omics platforms preventing a homogeneous fusion and integration of data.
- The high rate of metabolites that remain unidentified in untargeted metabolomics analysis, preventing a large-scale integration.
- The poor interpretability of the results by different computational genotype-phenotype models.
- Lack of integration of the knowledge in scientific literature and databases in an automated way into current genotype-phenotype association solutions.
- Non-biomedical sectors lack of holistic omics science-based integration tools.

Figure 7: View of GLOMICAVE platform page <https://glomicave.eu/platform/>

2.4 Business cases

GLOMICAVE platform is to be proven and validated in 6 business cases application, which will take place in three industries: animal, vegetal and environment.

ANIMAL BUSINESS CASES

The animal business cases are focused on livestock and the fertility level of these animals to optimise reproduction technologies efficiency in cattle and on the identification of genetic markers in beef cattle in order to improve beef production and meat quality.

- **Animal reproductive technology – Cattle fertility**

Currently there are no efficient methods to select competent embryos and recipients in cattle and between 40 and 60% of the pregnancies from embryo transfer do not reach birth. This business case aims to promote the **identification and validation of different biomarkers predicting pregnancy and birth in cattle in order to increase the knowledge of pathways involved in pregnancy establishing and fertility prediction in cattle embryo transfer.**

GLOMICAVE approach can help to develop and identify efficient biomarkers to select competent embryos and recipients in livestock sector, increasing the potential of pregnancy expectation.

- **Meat quality**

This case study has the objective to study and analyse the relationship between relevant phenotypes for the beef industry in order to improve the understanding of the meat production biological system.

The solution developed by GLOMICAVE will allow to identify functional differences associated with meat production traits, the best breeding steers allowing the improvement of cattle and to produce meat products with added value, increasing their final quality and price.

VEGETAL BUSINESS CASES

In these two business cases, GLOMICAVE platform will be studied and used to predict fruit quality and to identify biomarkers in order to improve yield and generate designer plants.

- **Fruit quality**

GLOMICAVE integrative platform will be used to find variables linked to fruit quality, such as genes, proteins and metabolites showing relationships between genotypes and fruit phenotypes that could be used as targets to improve genomic selection or agricultural practices.

- **Plant growth**

Cassava is a major tuber crop, cultivated and used specially in developing countries, which presents a good yield even in poor soils, an important drought tolerance and relevant industrial and nutritious applications. However, cassava has been scientifically relatively under-explored and under-investigated.

This study case will integrate multi-omics data from cassava using the GLOMICAVE platform with the aim to identify biomarkers for yield and, beyond that, potentially determine new mechanistic insights into storage root formation, both of which could improve yield and generate designer plants.

ENVIRONMENT BUSINESS CASES

The water-environment business cases are focused to identify and characterise of microbes and microbial consortia responsible for good performance in terms of microbial phosphorus removal and recovery, as well as for bioenergy production in anaerobic digestion.

- **Phosphate (P) removal and recovery**

Phosphate (P) is a scarce resource and a pollutant that should be removed from wastewater to protect the environment and recovered as an important P-resource (fertiliser as biosolids in agriculture, as struvite or other means).

In this business case, GLOMICAVE platform will be used to integrate data on microbial conversions in relation to biological P-removal by linking metagenomics, metatranscriptomics and metabolomics data to full-scale observations on P transformations and bioenergy production.

- **Bioenergy production**

This study case aims to validate the GLOMICAVE solution for predicting the ability (efficiency and rate) of the microbiome of an anaerobic sludge digester to remove organics and produce methane.

GLOMICAVE platform will integrate metagenomics and metatranscriptomics data obtained from full scale anaerobic digesters with operational data with the objective of linking microbial identity and function to methane productivity, yield and digested sludge quality.

BUSINESS CASES

Business cases

GLOMICAVE platform is to be proven and validated in 6 business cases application, which will take place in three industries: animal, vegetal and environment.

Animal

Focused on livestock and the fertility level of these animals to optimise reproduction technologies efficiency in cattle and to improve beef production and meat quality.

[More information >](#)

Vegetal

Focused on the prediction of fruit quality and the identification of biomarkers in order to improve yield and generate designer plants.

[More information >](#)

Environment

Focused on the identification and characterisation microbes and microbial consortia responsible for good performance in terms of microbial phosphorus removal and recovery.

[More information >](#)

Figure 8: View of Business cases page <https://glomicave.eu/business-cases/>

2.5 News & Events

This page will show articles on GLOMICAVE project advances and results, as well as general assembly meetings or articles written by partners on project topics. The page will also include an agenda announcing the upcoming events where GLOMICAVE consortium is attending or participating (meetings, fairs, conferences, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended.

2.5.1 Media

Section created to include the project's press releases and key media coverage on the project.

NEWS & EVENTS

News & Events

GLOMICAVE project Kicks off!

Meeting • December 2, 2019

Nulla a velit quis ex ornare rhoncus. Donec imperdiet risus justo, vel malesuada erat fermentum at. Morbi at laoreet mauris. Mauris lorem felis, gravida et vehicula congue, tempus vel justo.

[Read article](#)

Search

Recent Posts

GLOMICAVE project Kicks off December 2, 2019

Figure 9: View of News & Events page <https://qlomicave.eu/news-and-events/>

2.6 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@glomicave.eu has been created and is shown on the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

Contact us!

To contact with GLOMICAVE team please fill in the following form. We will get in touch with you as soon as possible.

Your Name (required)

Your Email (required)

Subject

Your Message

I have read and I accept the [privacy policy](#)

Figure 10: View of Contact page <https://glomicave.eu/contact/>

3. Layout

The GLOMICAVE website's menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the sight.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- GLOMICAVE logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Acces to Social Media platforms (Twitter, YouTube - when created).

Footer

- EU logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 952908. This website reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains"*.
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Contact info

Figure 11: GLOMICAVE website layout

4. Managing and updating policy

The **website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.**

The website will be updated from now on by the **Communication Leader Eurecat** together with the inputs sent by all partners every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved or there is other news worth publishing.

5. Analytics

The GLOMICAVE website has installed **Matomo** in the platform's back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services or third parties.

Figure 12: Matomo panel

6. Site hosting, installation and maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end and until two years after and adding content to the website. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that GLOMICAVE website is well positioned in the browsers.

7. Data protection

GLOMICAVE website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy on Annex.

8. Website KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of GLOMICAVE Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the website performance. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>4.000
	Number Pages Viewed		>10.000
	Number page / session		>1.0
	Number users		>2.000
	Avg. session time		>1.00 min

Table 1: GLOMICAVE website initial KPIs

ANNEX

1. Legal Warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.glomicave.eu FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

ACCESS TO THE WEBSITE

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

USE OF THE WEBSITE

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

OPERATION OF THE WEBSITE

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

LIABILITY

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

POLICY ON LINKS

a) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

b) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

INTELLECTUAL AND INDUSTRIAL PROPERTY RIGHTS OF THE CONTENT

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names ("distinctive signs") are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

APPLICABLE LEGISLATION

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

CONTACT

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

2. Cookies policy

WHAT ARE COOKIES AND WHY DO WE USE THEM ON THE WEBSITE?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES EXIST?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES DOES THE WEBSITE USE?

Necessary cookies

- **Name:** gdpr[allowed_cookies]
- **Provider:** glomicave.eu
- **Purpose:** stores cookies consent types
- **Expiry period:** 1 year

- **Name:** gdpr[consent_cookies]
- **Provider:** glomicave.eu
- **Purpose:** stores user cookies acceptance
- **Expiry period:** 1 year

Statistics cookies

- **Name:** _pk_ses.9.8960
- **Provider:** glomicave.eu
- **Purpose:** session cookies responsible for keeping the session active for 30 minutes.
- **Expiry period:** 1 day

- **Name:** _pk_id.9.8960
- **Provider:** glomicave.eu
- **Purpose:** user unique ID that is used to generate statistical data on how the visitor uses the website.
- **Expiry period:** 1 year and 1 month

Social Media cookies

- **Name:** _ga, _twitter_sess, _gid Eu_cn, Guest_id, Personalization_id, Tfw_exp.
- **Provider:** Twitter
- **Purpose:** Widget showing recent tweets published

The user can adjust the settings of the website cookies managed by the website publisher at the Privacy Preference center accessible from the footer.

HOW DO YOU DISABLE COOKIES IN A BROWSER?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered ad a Third-party cookies. For example, if the user chooses Google’s browser and use its option of translate full website, Google install cookies in the user’s computers that are not managed by the website publisher. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- **Information about cookies for** [Internet Explorer.](#)
- **Information about cookies for** [Mozilla Firefox.](#)
- **Information about cookies for** [Opera.](#)
- **Information about cookies for** [Google Chrome.](#)
- **Information about cookies for** [Safari.](#)

3. Privacy Policy

WHO IS THE DATA CONTROLLER FOR YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

FOR WHAT PURPOSE WILL BE PROCESSED YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Your personal data received through the contact form will be processed for the purpose of managing your query or request. However, the data collected as the result of the cookies installation, will be used for collecting statistical information on the browsing of users and improve the website based on their browsing habits. You may consult further information about the cookies purposes and its data treatment at the Cookies Policy

On our website, there may be several forms that collects your personal data for specific purposes. In those cases, you will be previously informed about the specific data treatment information to each case, and your specific consent shall be sought.

IS IT MANDATORY TO PROVIDE ALL THE INFORMATION REQUESTED IN THE FORMS ON THE WEBSITE?

The user must complete the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

HOW LONG WILL YOUR PERSONAL DATA BE RETAINED FOR?

The personal data obtained, will be kept for the duration of the purposes for which it was collected for and its erasure is not requested, and consent is not revoked. The personal data, also, will be kept, in any case, during the legal term applicable.

WHAT IS THE LAWFUL BASIS FOR US TO PROCESS YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

WHAT RECIPIENTS WILL YOUR DATA BE SHARED WITH?

The Personal data received through the forms of the website may be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the latest news about the project through periodic newsletters. You may consult the list of members [here](#).

The personal data may be shared to third-parties whose develop services to the Data Controller, those ones who has access to the personal data will not treat the personal data fort their own or different purposes and they will not sold or rent them.

The personal data will not be passed on to any other third-parties, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

WHAT ARE YOUR RIGHTS REGARDING YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data to be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org.

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response, and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

AUTOMATED DECISIONS

The personal data shall not be submitted to automated decisions.

The personal data may be processed to create profiles according to the cookies that has been consented to installed by the user.

INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS

The personal data shall not be submitted to international transfers out of the European Union. However, the Data Controller may have several suppliers that develop services out of the UE, in those cases, Fundació Eurecat shall assure that the personal data shall be treated with the legal requirements through agreement that may include standard contractual clauses or privacy certification.

WHAT SECURITY MEASURES HAS THE INSTITUTION IMPLEMENTED?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

SOCIAL MEDIA

GLOMICAVE, a project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which GLOMICAVE has an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

4. Privacy information contact form

Pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679, of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the relevant State regulations, FUNDACIÓ Eurecat, the controller, hereby provides the following basic information regarding data protection:

- **Controller:**

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT

G66210345

Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23 – 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), Spain
legal@eurecat.org

Details of the data protection officer: dpo@eurecat.org

- **Purpose of the processing of your personal data:** Managing your request or queries
- **Legal Basis:** The basis for the processing is the specific consent granted by the data subject for this activity.
- **Recipients:** The data will be disclosed to the partners involved in the GLOMICAVE project; you may consult them at: <https://glomicave.eu/partners/>
- **Rights:** You may access, rectify or erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing and portability of the data by contacting the controller at its address or the email address legal@eurecat.org.
- **Storage:** The data will be stored for the term required to render the data treatment purpose

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT hereby informs you that it meets all the requirements stipulated by the data protection regulations and has in place all the technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of personal data. Moreover, in the event of any breach by the controller in the processing of your personal data, you are entitled to file a claim with the Spanish Data Protection Agency.